

Effect of Summer Induce Oxidative Stress in Bull Fertility

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Abstract

Summer-induced heat stress is the primary cause of fertility and has severe implications for livestock output, animal welfare, and overall health. Within the Thermoneutral zone (TNZ) range, animals maintain a physiological body temperature of 38.4°C to 39.1°C. Testicular tissue can become hypoxic and experience oxidative tissue stress if this is not accompanied by adequate blood flow to maintain an adequate amount of oxygenation. The awkwardness between generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) and detoxifying with antioxidants is known as oxidative stress. Almost all facets of cellular activity are impacted by reactive oxygen species (ROS). Oxidative stress is a major cause of heat stress in germ cells and leads to apoptosis, mostly in spermatocytes and early spermatids. There are correlations with decreased fertility due to DNA damage, early cell death, protein malfunction, and lipid peroxidation, all of which easily occur in spermatozoa if there is an oxidative stress condition. Heat stress affects different cellular components of the testis approximately 14–21 days after exposure. Testicular heat stress first causes an increase in morphological defects, followed by increased sperm lipid peroxidation, affecting mitochondrial membrane potential, sperm motility, plasma membrane integrity, and sperm DNA fragmentation.

Keywords: Bull fertility, Cellular damage, Heat stress, Oxidative stress, ROS.

Introduction

The bovine Thermoneutral Zone (TNZ) ranges in temperature from 16°C to 25°C. Animals maintain a physiological body temperature of 38.4°C to 39.1°C within this range. Bulls under summer heat stress have higher respiratory rates, higher rectal temperatures, and reduced testicular weight. The quality of bulls' semen and embryonic development are both negatively impacted by the high ambient temperature and humidity throughout the summer. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are produced in response to summertime heat stress, which damages DNA and causes germ cells to apoptosis. Sperm motility, morphology, and fertility are negatively impacted by elevated testicular temperature, with the severity and persistence of the effect being connected. All types of testicular cells are affected by systemic heat stress or localised testicular warming, but germ cells are more sensitive than Sertoli or Leydig cells. Heat stress increases the development of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which harms cells and is bad for the sperm membrane (because of its high level of unsaturated fatty acids), poor motility, and male infertility. It took almost 8 weeks for the semen quality to get back to normal.

Oxidative stress

The awkwardness between the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and detoxification by antioxidants is known as oxidative stress. Since sperm cells perform their work in aerobic situations, oxygen is a basic component for supporting sperm function. ROS are chemically reactive atoms (H_2O_2 , O_2^- , OH^- and $^{\cdot}OCl$) and they are exceedingly reactive due to the nearness of unpaired valence shell electrons. Ordinarily, productions of low and controlled concentrations of reactive oxygen species offer assistance in capacitation, hyperactivation, acrosomal responses, and signaling forms for suitable fertilization. But the intemperate generation of ROS altogether caused oxidative stress, and as a result, sperm function declined. But the intemperate generation of ROS altogether caused oxidative stress, and as a result, sperm function declined.

Mechanism of heat stress and ROS production in testis

Effects of ROS and oxidative stress

- Damage of DNA and RNA damage of sperm cells.
- Lipid peroxidation
- Denaturation of protein or alteration of protein structure
- Mitochondria of sperm destroyed etc.

Effects of heat stress on different cellular components of testis:

Due to heat stress in the cell membrane, changes in fluidity/stability, alteration in structure, impairment of ion transport, and modulation of the trans-membrane efflux pump; in the cytoplasm, impairment of protein synthesis, denaturation of protein structure and function, aggregation of proteins,

and induction of heat-shock protein (HSP) synthesis; depolarization of the mitochondrial membrane potential; depletion of ATP production; production of ROS; disruption of Ca^{2+} transport across the mitochondrial membrane; impairment of DNA synthesis; inhibition of DNA repair enzymes; alteration of the Protamination is such an important aspect of sperm chromatin condensation. Protamine deficiency affects spermatozoa, especially in the population of spermatozoa that are at the spermiogenic and meiotic stages of development. Heat stress affects sperm remodeling procedures (protamine-DNA compaction), which results in a higher incidence of protamine deficiency or loosely protaminated spermatozoa in heat-stressed ejaculates. CS and SDH could be a better indicator of spermatogenesis; the number of mitochondria and abundance of the mRNA population of CS were reported in high fertility bull's spermatozoa as compared to low-fertility bull's spermatozoa. The lower expression of SDH and CS (as a representative of mitochondrial respiratory activity, number or volume, and transcription activities) might be due to the limitation of mitochondrial respiratory activity from heat stress, which directly affects the energy (ATP) metabolism for sperm motility and results in poor semen quality during the summer season. Testicular heat stress first causes an increase in morphological defects, followed by increased sperm lipid peroxidation, thereby affecting mitochondrial membrane potential, sperm motility, plasma membrane integrity, and sperm DNA fragmentation.

Effect of heat stress in different sperm characteristics

Effect on sperm motility: Oxidative stress due to heat stress attacks the high-PUFA sperm membrane and causes lipid peroxidation by the formation of peroxy radicals, MDA, and alkoxy radicals, which destabilise the plasma membrane by abstracting hydrogen atoms from PUFA and, as a result, abduct lipid metabolites with flagella protein and mitochondrial electron transport protein. Formation of ATP is disrupted, and a lack of flagellar protein formation reduces sperm motility.

Effect on sperm DNA integrity: Under oxidative stress due to heat stress, different ROS radicals like hydroxyl ($\text{OH}^{\cdot}$) bind with the double bond of DNA bases and abstract hydrogen ions from deoxyribose sugar. Breakage of strands and alteration of bases Oxidation of guanine and pyrimidine bases leads to transversion mutations due to their ability to pair with adenine and cytosine bases.

Heat stress on spermatogenesis: Heat stress increases testicular temperature, leading to sperm abnormalities. The proportion, severity, and moment of appearance of abnormal sperm in the ejaculate depend on the intensity and duration of heat stress, and the developmental stages of affected germ cells Mild, short-term heat stress can significantly affect sperm motility 14 to 21 days after exposure, as a result of insult to the spermatid and spermatocyte stages of development, where formation of the flagellum occurs.

Sperm cell apoptosis: Heat stress affects somatic cells less than cells with strong mitotic activity, such as cancer cells and germ cells. Numerous studies have demonstrated that ROS contribute to heat-induced germ cell harm via inducing apoptosis. The effect of heat on spermatogenesis is not only stage-specific but also cell-specific. The most heat-sensitive spermatocytes were pachytene and early spermatids at stages I through IV, diplotene and dividing spermatocytes at stages XII through XIV. The Bcl-2 family, Fas, Fas ligand, and p53 are only a few of the genes involved in the intricate process of germ cell death, which is crucial to healthy spermatogenesis. Molecular chaperones known as heat shock proteins (HSPs) have been found in practically all sorts of organisms. However, HSP production is inhibited above a specific threshold temperature (usually above 42°C), which causes exponential cell death.

Conclusion

Summer induced oxidative stress chronologically damages the sperm by affecting mitochondrial membrane potential, sperm motility, plasma membrane integrity, and sperm DNA fragmentation, all of which ultimately led to infertility in bulls, as climate change is a global issue and has negative effects on animal welfare and productivity. So, we need to put more effort into this aspect, or new strategies will need to be developed to solve this problem.

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